

STUDIES ON THE NATURE OF THE RACEMIC MODIFICATIONS OF
OPTICALLY ACTIVE COMPOUNDS IN THE SOLID STATE. PART XI.
PHENYL-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-CHLOROPHENYLIMINOCAMPHORS (*d* & *dl*)
AND PHENYL-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-CHLOROPHENYL-
AMINOCAMPHORS (*d* & *dl*)

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The nature of the racemic forms of phenyl-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-chlorophenyliminocamphors and phenyl-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-chlorophenylaminocamphors has been investigated by the application of the freezing point (melting point)—composition method of Roozeboom. It is found that the racemic forms of *o*-chlorophenylimino- and -aminocamphors are solid solutions, whereas the remaining racemic forms are true *dl*-compounds.

m-Chlorophenylamino-*dl*-camphor exists in dimorphic forms (α and β). A new method for the determination of transformation (transition) temperature of the dimorphic forms, based on the melting point-composition diagram, has been developed. The temperature of transformation of α into β forms, in this case, is found to be 116.1°.

All the racemic forms except phenylimino- and -aminocamphors are new compounds. Among the optically active forms, *o*-chlorophenylamino-*d*-camphor and *m*-chlorophenylamino-*d*-camphor are new substances.

We have in this communication discussed the nature of the racemic modification of phenyl-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-chlorophenylimino- and -aminocamphors. The chlorophenylimino- and chlorophenylamino-*dl*-camphors (*o*-, *m*-, *p*-) as well as the *o*- and *m*-chlorophenylamino-*d*-camphors are new compounds. *m*-Chlorophenylamino-*dl*-camphor exists in dimorphic forms (α and β).

The enantiomorphic modifications may occur in equimolecular proportions to constitute what is known as a racemic form. Three cases are possible:

(i) A racemic 'conglomerate' or mixture of *d*- and *l*-isomers in equimolecular proportions (Type I).

(ii) A racemic compound (*dl*) composed of one molecule of each of the optical and opposite isomers (Type II).

(iii) A racemic solid solution or mixed crystals of equimolecular proportions of *d*- and *l*-forms (Type III).

There are three methods of distinguishing racemic forms; two of them, due to Roozeboom (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 537; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, 26, 494) and Bruni (*Gazzetta*, 1900, 30, 35) are physical: Freezing-point or melting-point method and Solubility method. The third method, Biochemical, is due to Singh *et al.* (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1944, 14, 171).

Solubility-Composition Diagrams

Roozeboom (*loc. cit.*) and Bruni (*loc. cit.*) have theoretically discussed, from the standpoint of Phase rule, the solubility relationships of optically active isomers, their racemic mixtures, compounds and solid solutions. The solubility-composition isotherms,

which they had deduced theoretically, had not been obtained experimentally, until Singh and Perti (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 22A, 170) in the case of camphor- β -sulphonic acid and Singh and Nayar (*ibid.*, 1945, 22A, 46; 1947, 26A, 368) in the cases of camphoric acid and camphor carboxylic acid supplied these experimental curves. In each case three curves were obtained, which conclusively proved that the racemic acids were true (*dl*) compounds.

The Melting point-Composition Method of Roozeboom

We have employed the melting point-composition method as it is very convenient and requires only small amounts of *dextro* (or *laevo*) and *racemic* forms. It consists in preparing the melting point-composition diagram. On the axis of composition are shown the percentage compositions of mixtures of *dextro* (or *laevo*) and *racemic* forms and on the vertical axis, the melting points of the mixtures.

In the case of the *racemic mixture* (Type I), the melting point of each optical isomer will be lowered by the addition of increasing amounts of the racemic form till the eutectic point (the melting point of the racemic form) is reached. Thus, there will be two symmetrical curves, formed by joining the melting points of each of the optical isomers and the racemic form (racemic mixture). No such cases have, however, been observed in the present investigation.

In the case of the *racemic compound* (*racemate*), three curves will be obtained with two symmetrical eutectic points -*invariant points*- and a central maximum point (Type II). The maximum point is the melting point of the racemic compound (*dl*).

The *mixed crystal* or *solid solution* type of a racemic substance (Type III) will exhibit a single continuous curve, formed by joining the melting points of optically active and opposite forms and their racemic modifications. If the two solids (*d* and *l*) are completely soluble in each other, only one solid phase can exist, for a homogeneous solid solution constitutes a single solid phase, and only one liquid phase can form. Since the maximum number of phases is two, for a condensed system, the minimum number of degrees of freedom, including pressure, is two; hence an *invariant* system is impossible, and there will be no *singular point*, i.e., *discontinuity*, on the phase diagram. Such freezing point (melting point)-composition diagrams will fall into three groups: (a) The melting points of all the compositions may lie on a straight line joining the melting points of the two optical antipodes; (b) the continuous curve may have a maximum or (c) a minimum. Examples of these three cases are known, e.g., *d*- and *l*-camphoroxime and *d*- and *l*-borneol have the same melting point for all mixtures as that of the pure components. The melting point-composition curves are, thus, horizontal straight lines, parallel to the composition axis. The melting point-composition curves with a maximum are found in the cases of *d*- and *l*-carvoxime and *d*- and *l*- α -bromocamphor. The melting point-composition curves with a minimum, as in the cases of *o*-chlorophenylimino- and-amino camphors, are described in this paper (Figs. 1 and 2).

In the present work we have employed *d*- and *dl*- forms in preparing the melting point-composition diagrams, and have reproduced the other half of the curve (*dl-l*) as the true mirror image of the experimentally determined half portion of the diagram

(*d-dl*). The mirror image portion of the diagram (*dl-l*) is represented by broken curves in Figs. 1-8. Since each of the diagrams is symmetrical, only one of the enantiomorphs together with the racemic modification is necessary for the study.

Melting Point-Composition Curves

The substances described in this paper furnished the melting point-composition diagrams which belong to types II and III, discussed above.

FIG. 1
o-Chlorophenylaminocamphors.

FIG. 2
o-Chlorophenylaminocamphors.

o-Chlorophenylimino- and -aminocamphors.—The melting point-composition diagrams in these cases have a minimum, but there is no singular point in these curves, which are continuous. This therefore indicates that these racemic forms are solid solutions (type III). In both the cases the portion of the diagram, E_1RE_2 , is almost horizontal. The curves DE_1RE_2L are continuous, without any singular point (Figs. 1 & 2).

m-Chlorophenyliminocamphors.—The melting point-composition diagram (Fig. 3) of these compounds belongs to type II. It has a central maximum (R) and two minima (E_1 , E_2). Thus, it consists of three curves DE_1 , E_1RE_2 , and E_2L . The racemic form is therefore a true *dl*-compound. The central portion of the diagram occupies a large area and the *dl-d* portion of the curve is also fairly steep; its range of stability is therefore large. The eutectic points, E_1 and E_2 , are not sharp and well defined, which indicates that the racemic compound and the optical isomers form solid solutions in these regions.

FIG. 3
m-Chlorophenyliminocamphors.

m-Chlorophenylaminocamphors.—*m*-Chlorophenylamino-*dl*-camphor exists in dimorphic forms (α and β). These forms can be mutually transformed into each other, as described in the experimental part.

β -Form.—The melting point-composition diagram ($DE'_1TR'T'E'_2L$) of β -form (Fig. 4, β -form, Table I) has a central maximum R' and two minima, E'_1 and E'_2 . It consists of three curves: DE'_1 , $E'_1TR'T'E'_2$, and E'_2L . It is therefore a true *dl*-compound. Its range of stability is large as it occupies a great portion of the diagram, and the curve *dl-d* is fairly steep. The eutectic points, E'_1 , and E'_2 , are not sharp and well defined. It indicates that the racemic compound and its optical isomers form solid solutions in these regions.

FIG. 4
m-Chlorophenylaminocamphors.

α -Form.—The diagram of this compound (Fig. 4, α -form) is very interesting. Its general shape is similar to that of the β -form, and consists of three curves: DE_1 , $E_1TR'T'E_2$ and E_2L . It is therefore a true *dl*-compound.

The melting points of α -form (106.6°) and β -form (116.8°) with admixtures of 3, 5 and 7% of *d*-form are identical, namely, 116.6° , 116.3° and 116.1° respectively (vide Table I, Fig. 4); in other words, the mixed melting point curves of α - and β -form with *d*-form are identical in this range. With 8, 9 and 10% admixtures of *d*-form with the α -form (*dl*), the melting points are about 0.2° higher than those of β -form with *d*-form in the above mentioned proportions. With 30% admixture the melting points are: α -form, 105.5° and β -form, 100.2° . As the amount of *d*-form is further increased, the melting points of the mixtures of *d*-form with α -form are only slightly higher than those with the β -form. It may, however, be noted that the melting point-composition curve of α -form always lies above that of the β -form, except for the composition range, 0% *d* to 7% *d* in which case it is identical with that of the β -form. The point at which the two melting point-composition curves of α - and β -forms meet is the transformation (transition) temperature of α -into β -form, and is found to be 116.1° . It is clearly shown in the Inset of Fig. 4 (Fig. 4a, drawn on a larger scale).

The α -form is the *metastable form*, as it changes into the β -form on heating. According to Ostwald's rule it has higher energy of activation which is released, when it is transformed into the β -modification.

The melting points of the mixtures of *d*-form, with the α -form (*metastable form*) are higher than those with the β -form (*stable form*) except as indicated above. This is brought about by the greater energy of activation associated with the α -form: The depression in melting points of α -form due to addition of different amounts of *d*-form should have, according to the freezing point equation, caused the melting point

curve of α -form to be below that of β -form, had there been no change of α -form into the β -form. But since α -form changes into the β -form under the experimental conditions, its melting point curve should have been identical with that of the β -form. The extra energy of activation released during transformation, however, raises the temperature of the melt of the mixtures of the α -form with the d -form above that of the β -form with d -form. Its curve therefore lies above that of β -form. This holds if the transformation temperature is *above* the melting points of the mixtures. If it is *below* the melting point of the mixtures, the two curves will be identical. Based on this principle, a method has been devised to determine the temperature of transformation for the dimorphic forms, as described in the following section.

TABLE I

m-Chlorophenylaminocamphors (α & β) (Fig. 4)

Mixed melting-points of the racemic modification with d -form (Type II, compound).

Weight % of d -form.	Weight % of dl -form. (a).	Mixed m.p.	Wt. % of d -form. (b).	Mixed m.p.	Weight % of d -form.	Weight % of dl -form. (a).	Mixed m.p.	Wt. % of dl -form. (b).	Mixed m.p.
100	0	95.8°	0	95.8°	30	70	105.5°	70	100.2°
90	10	93.6°	10	92.4°	20	80	112.6°	80	108.1°
85	15	93.4°	...	...	10	90	115.5°	90	115.2°
80	20	93.4°	20	92.2°	9	91	115.6°	91	115.4°
75	25	93.1°	...	...	8	92	115.7°	92	115.5°
70	30	93.3°	30	92.2°	7	93	116.1°	93	116.1°
65	35	93.5°	...	...	6	94	116.3°	94	116.3°
60	40	93.6°	40	93.0°	5	95	116.3°	95	116.3°
50	50	94.4°	50	94.0°	3	97	116.6°	97	116.6°
40	60	97.3°	60	96.6°	0	100	106.6°	0	116.8°

* After melting and resolidification it changes to 116.8° (β).

Determination of Transformation (Transition) Temperature of α - into β -Form

There are seven methods described by Findlay ("Phase-Rule and its Applications", 1935, p. 306) for the determination of transformation (transition) temperatures of dimorphic and polymorphic forms. We describe in this paper a very elegant and convenient method for the determination of transformation temperature based on the melting point-composition diagram of the metastable and stable forms with a third substance, as described above.

If the transition temperature is *above* the melting points of the mixtures of β -form with a third substance (d -form), the curve of metastable form (α) will always lie above that of stable form (β). If, however, the transformation temperature is *below* the melting points of the mixtures, the melting point curves of α -form and the β -form with d -form will be identical. The point where the two curves meet will be the transforma-

tion temperature. By applying this method it is found that the transformation temperature of α - into β -form of *m*-chlorophenylamino-*dl*-camphor is 116.1° (Fig. 4, and Inset 4a). *d*-Camphor- β -sulphonylphenylamide, which also occurs in dimorphic forms, α (m.p. 115.0°) and β (m.p. 120.6°), has recently been investigated by Singh and Verma (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1956, **43A**, 21) by the application of this method.

p-Chlorophenyliminocamphors.—The melting point-composition diagram consists of three curves DE_1 , E_1RE_2 and E_2L , with a central maximum (R) and two minima (E_1 and E_2) (Fig. 5). The racemic form is therefore a true *dl*-compound, but its range of stability is very small, viz., 90% *dl*:100% *dl*. The eutectic points, E_1 and E_2 , are sharp and well defined. It is interesting to note that the addition of 10% *dl*-form to the pure *d*-component lowers its melting point by 2.8° , whereas the addition of the same amount of the *dl*-form to the mixture consisting of 30% *d*:70% *dl* produces a remarkably small lowering in its melting point, viz., 0.2° . This clearly points to the fact that the deviations from the freezing point equation are governed by different variables at different points on the curve DE_1 .

FIG. 5

p-Chlorophenyliminocamphors.

p-Chlorophenylaminocamphors.—The melting point-composition diagram in this case also consists of three curves (Fig. 6), with a maximum point (R) and two minima (E_1 and E_2). The racemic form is therefore a true *dl*-compound. It occupies a large portion of the diagram, and the curve RE_1 is fairly steep. The *dl*-compound is therefore fairly stable, and its range of stability is large. The eutectic points, E_1 and E_2 , are not sharp and well defined, which indicates that the racemic compound and the optical isomers form solid solutions in these regions.

FIG. 6

p-Chlorophenylaminocamphors.

Phenyliminocamphors and Phenylaminocamphors.—The melting point-composition diagrams of these two substances are very similar. Each of these curves has a central maximum (R) and two minima, E₁ and E₂, which shows that the racemic forms are true *dl*-compounds. The central portions of the diagrams (Figs. 7 and 8) are large, and the curves RE₁ are fairly steep. This indicates that these racemic compounds are stable, and their stability is great. In the case of phenyliminocamphors (Fig. 7) the eutectic points, E₁ and E₂, are somewhat sharp, whereas those in the case of phenylaminocamphors are not sharp, and well defined (Fig. 8). It therefore appears that phenylamino-*dl*-camphor forms solid solutions with the *d*-isomeride in this region.

FIG. 7

Phenylimino-camphors,

FIG. 8

Phenylaminocamphor.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chlorophenylimino-dl-camphors (o-, m- & p-)

These racemic compounds are new substances and were prepared as follows :

p-Chlorophenylimino-dl-camphor was prepared by heating together dl-camphor-quinone and *p*-chloroaniline in equimolecular proportions in presence of anhydrous sodium sulphate on a water-bath for 6 to 7 hours. The reaction product was cooled and extracted with rectified spirit. The compound was precipitated by dilution with water. It was recrystallised from hot aqueous ethyl alcohol as sulphur-yellow needles, m.p. 132-33°. (Found : N, 5.3. $C_{16}H_{18}ONCl$ requires N, 5.08 per cent).

It is readily soluble in chloroform, benzene, acetone, pyridine and ethyl acetate, sparingly so in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol, and insoluble in water.

The *d*-isomeride, m.p. 140-141°, was prepared in the same way as by Forster and Thornley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 942).

m-Chlorophenylimino-dl-camphor was prepared in the same way as the *p*-isomeride. The crude product on crystallisation from hot aqueous ethyl alcohol (50-70%) furnished yellow prisms, m.p. 123-24°. (Found : N, 5.07. $C_{16}H_{18}ONCl$ requires N, 5.08 per cent).

The compound is readily soluble in chloroform, benzene, acetone, pyridine and ethyl acetate, sparingly so in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol and insoluble in water.

The *d*-isomer, m.p. 119-20°, was prepared according to Singh and Mazumdar (*ibid.*, 1919, 115, 572) who, however, record the m.p. as 123-24°.

The relative order of solubility is the same as that of the *dl*-isomer. (Found : N, 5.15. $C_{16}H_{18}ONCl$ requires N, 5.08 per cent).

o-Chlorophenylimino-dl-camphor was prepared by two methods : (i) by using the free base and (ii) by using the hydrochloride of the base. In the second case the reaction was completed in shorter time and the yield of the compound was also better.

(i). *dl*-Camphorquinone and *o*-chloroaniline, in equimolecular proportions, were condensed together on the water-bath for 48 to 55 hours in the presence of anhydrous sodium sulphate. The reaction product was cooled and extracted with rectified spirit. The compound was precipitated on dilution with water. It was crystallised from hot aqueous alcohol (50-70%) as silky yellow needles, m.p. 113-14°.

(ii). *dl*-Camphorquinone and *o*-chloroaniline hydrochloride, in equimolecular proportions, were heated together on the water-bath, maintained at 80-90°, in the presence of excess of anhydrous sodium acetate for 6 to 7 hours. The reaction product was cooled and extracted with rectified spirit, and the compound precipitated by dilution with water. It was recrystallised from hot aqueous ethyl alcohol as silky yellow needles, m.p. 113-14°. The melting point of a mixture of the specimens prepared by the two methods was not depressed.

The compound is highly soluble in chloroform, benzene, acetone, pyridine and ethyl acetate, sparingly so in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol and insoluble in water. (Found : N, 5.03. $C_{16}H_{19}ONCl$ requires N, 5.08 per cent).

The *d*-isomer, m.p. 123-24°, was prepared in the same way as the racemic form. Singh and Mazumdar (*loc. cit.*) reported its m.p. 128°. (Found : N, 5.24. $C_{16}H_{19}ONCl$ requires N, 5.08 per cent).

Chlorophenylamino-dl-camphors (o-, m- & p-)

The racemic compounds as well as their *d*-isomerides (except the *para* isomeride) are new substances and were prepared by the reduction of the corresponding chlorophenyliminocamphors with zinc dust and alkali, as given below :

p-Chlorophenylamino-*dl*-camphor was prepared by the reduction of *p*-chlorophenylimino-*dl*-camphor in ethereal solution with zinc dust and 10% aqueous KOH solution. The solution was shaken in a closed bottle till colorless. The ethereal layer was separated and evaporated off to dryness. The residue was recrystallised thrice from dilute aqueous ethyl alcohol (50-70%) as hexagonal plates, m.p. 138°. (Found : N, 5.3. $C_{16}H_{20}ONCl$ requires N, 5.04 per cent).

It is highly soluble in chloroform, benzene, acetone, pyridine and ethyl acetate, sparingly so in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol, and insoluble in water.

Forster and Thornley (*loc. cit.*) prepared the *d*-isomeride by acid reduction, but we found that by this method the yield was poor, and it also took much longer time for the reaction to be completed. The m.p. 97-98°, however, agrees with that reported by them (98°).

The relative order of solubility in different solvents is the same as that of the *dl*-form.

m-Chlorophenylamino-*dl*-camphor was obtained in two dimorphic forms: α -form, m.p. 106-108° and β -form, m.p. 116-18°.

α -Form was prepared by the reduction of an ethereal solution of *m*-chlorophenylimino-*dl*-camphor with zinc dust and 10% aqueous KOH solution. The crude product was thrice recrystallised from hot aqueous ethyl alcohol (50-70%) as rectangular plates, m.p. 106-108°. (Found : N, 5.3. $C_{16}H_{20}ONCl$ requires N, 5.04 per cent).

The compound is readily soluble in chloroform, benzene, acetone, pyridine and ethyl acetate, sparingly so in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol and insoluble in water.

β -Form was first obtained on reduction of *m*-chlorophenylimino-*dl*-camphor by zinc dust and 10% aqueous KOH solution. The crude product melted at 114-116°. On twice recrystallisation from aqueous alcohol (50%) it was converted into the α -form m.p. 106-108°. On recrystallisation from *absolute* ethyl alcohol or methyl alcohol, a product containing crystals of both the forms was obtained.

The β -form was also obtained by heating the α -form at its melting point. (Found : N, 5.2. $C_{16}H_{20}ONCl$ requires N, 5.04 per cent).

The relative order of solubility in different solvents is the same as that of the α -form.

Both the forms are very susceptible to oxidation. The ethereal solution on exposure to air immediately turns brown. The evaporation of ethereal solution was therefore carried out in an inert atmosphere (coal gas).

Mutual Transformation of α - and β -Forms

(i) The α -form is converted into the β -form with or without a trace of β -form at its melting point.

(ii) The β -form is converted into the α -form by crystallisation from dilute aqueous alcohol (50%).

(iii) Crystallisation of α - or β -form from *absolute* methyl alcohol or ethyl alcohol affords a mixture of α - and β -forms.

The above mentioned transformations may be represented as below :

The *d*-isomeride was prepared in the same way as the *dl*-isomer by alkaline reduction of the corresponding iminocamphor. The crude product was crystallised from dilute aqueous ethyl alcohol (50-70%) as rectangular plates, m.p. 95-96°. (Found : N, 5.11. $C_{16}H_{20}ONCl$ requires N, 5.04 per cent).

The relative order of solubility of the *d*-form in different solvents is the same as that of the *dl*-isomeride. The *dextro* form, however, does not exhibit dimorphism.

o-Chlorophenylamino-*dl*-camphor was obtained in the same way as the *para* and *meta* isomerides by alkaline reduction of *o*-chlorophenylimino-*dl*-camphor. The crude product was recrystallised thrice from hot aqueous ethyl alcohol (50%) as rectangular plates, m.p. 118°

The compound is freely soluble in chloroform, benzene, acetone, pyridine and ethyl acetate, sparingly so in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol and insoluble in water. (Found : N, 5.24. $C_{16}H_{20}ONCl$ requires N, 5.04 per cent).

The *d*-form was prepared in the same way as the *dl*-isomer by alkaline reduction of *o*-chlorophenylimino-*d*-camphor. The crude product was crystallised twice from dilute aqueous ethyl alcohol (50-70%) as rectangular plates, m.p. 146-47°. (Found : N, 5.2. $C_{16}H_{20}ONCl$ requires N, 5.04 per cent). The relative order of solubility of the compound is the same as the *dl*-isomeride.

Phenylimino-dl-camphor and *phenylamino-dl-camphor* were prepared according to the methods of Singh *et al.* (this *Journal*, 1931, 8, 95).

Phenylimino-d-camphor and *phenylamino-d-camphor* were prepared according to the method of Forster and Thornley (*loc. cit.*).

The melting point-composition diagrams were prepared as follows :

An intimate mixture of known composition of racemic form and *dextro* isomeride was prepared by taking exact weights of the components in different proportions in an agate mortar and thorough mixing and grinding. Six determinations of the melting point (capillary-tube method) of each mixture were made with Siebert and Kuhn thermometers graduated to 0.2° and the mean value was taken as the m.p. of the mixture. The results are plotted as the melting point-composition diagram in Figs. 1-8. The tables of data recording m.p. and percentage composition by weight of different mixtures, except in one case, are omitted for the sake of economy of space.

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